

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS OF ENSURING FOOD SECURITY IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBALIZATION AND CLIMATE CHANGE

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***Аннотация.** В статье рассмотрены оценка, состояния продовольственной проблемы и пути её решения в XXI веке определяя наиболее уязвимые страны мира, которые страдают от нехватки продовольствия. Оценить влияние глобализации, климатических изменений на продовольственное обеспечение на планете изучая способы производства продовольствия в переменных климатических условиях обеспечивая устойчивое развитие страны.*

***Ключевые слова:** глобализация, продовольственная безопасность, климатические изменения и тд.*

***Abstract.** The article examines the assessment of the state of the food problem and ways to solve it in the 21st century, identifying the most vulnerable countries in the world that suffer from food shortages. Assess the impact of globalization and climate change on the food supply on the planet by studying methods of food production in variable climatic conditions ensuring sustainable development of the country.*

***Keywords:** Agriculture, food security, financial security, principles of financing, etc.*

***Anastasiya.** Maqolada oziq-ovqat muammosi holatini baholash va uni xxi asrda hal qilish yo'llari, oziq-ovqat tanqisligidan aziyat chekayotgan dunyodagi eng zaif davlatlar aniqlangan. Mamlakatning barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlaydigan o'zgaruvchan iqlim sharoitida ozi'-ovqat mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish usullari o'rganish orgali globallashuv va iqlim o'zgarishining sayyoramizdagi oziq-ovqat ta'minotiga ta'sirini baholash.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** globallashuv, oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi, iqlim o'zgarishi va boshqalar.*

INTRODUCTION

2000 years ago, the hardworking and brave peoples of the Eurasian continent opened several routes of trade and human communications that connected the civilizations of Asia, Europe, and Africa, ensuring the reliability and availability of food supplies. Subsequently, they were called historical trade routes that shaped world history. Trade routes have been formed since ancient times when traders from different countries transported their goods to sell and buy them in other countries. Goods were only available where they were made, so traders had to travel long distances to deliver them to buyers in other countries. These trade routes contributed to cultural exchange, as well as the development of the economy, culture and art, religion, and gastronomy, associated with the development of its food complex, with the general state of the national and world economy. The paths that were formed in ancient times are as follows [1]:

1. The Silk Road is the most famous trade route in the world. The Great Silk Road was a caravan road that connected East Asia with the Mediterranean in ancient times and the Middle Ages. It was primarily used to export silk from China, which is where its name comes from. The path was laid in the 2nd century BC., the term "Silk Road" was introduced by the German geographer Ferdinand von Richthofen in 1877. During the journey from east to west, silk and spices passed through dozens of hands. In this regard, historians are talking about the travel of

goods and technologies, not people. Mainly donkeys and camels were used for transportation. The intensity of trade relations decreased after the ousting of the Romans from the Middle East and the beginning of the Arab conquests. During the periodic Byzantine-Iranian wars, the rules of Persia blocked the caravan routes to cause maximum damage to the Byzantine economy. Difficulties with the delivery of goods also arose in the early Arab period, especially after the defeat of the Chinese in the Battle of Talas, which forced them to leave Central Asia. Silk, although the main one, was far from the only product transported along the transcontinental route. Khuttal horses, highly valued in China, military equipment, gold and silver, semi-precious stones and glassware, leather and wool, carpets and cotton fabrics, exotic fruits – watermelons and peaches, fat-tailed sheep and hunting dogs, leopards and lions. From China, caravans brought porcelain and metal utensils, lacquerware and cosmetics, tea, and rice. In the travel bags of merchants, one could find elephant tusks, rhinoceros` horns, tortoiseshells, spices, and much more. The Great Silk Road played a major role in the development of economic and cultural ties between the peoples of Western Asia, the Caucasus, Central Asia, and China. He served as a conduit for the spread of technology and innovation, including dance, music, fine arts, architecture, religious Christianity, Buddhism, Islam, Manichaeism, technology for the production of silk, as well as gunpowder, paper, etc.

2. The Spice Road is an overland part of one of the oldest trade routes on earth, connecting India, the Spice Islands, and East Africa with the countries of the Mediterranean. It started from the ports of the Arabian and Red Seas, where goods were reloaded onto caravans that went through Petra to the Mediterranean coast. To facilitate trade, Queen Hatshepsut, the pharaohs Senusret III and Necho I, and King Darius I, attempted to dig a canal connecting the Red Sea with the Mediterranean. During the time of King Solomon, the land part of the spice road went to the coast of the Gulf of Eilat in the area of the city of Etzion-Gaver, present-day Eilat (Israel).

Along this route, not only spices were delivered from the Spice Islands, cinnamon, ginger, and pepper from India, but also valuable wood and ivory from East Africa, silk from China, gold, silver, and precious stones. Depending on the military-political situation, certain sections of the spice road, like any other trade route, could be shifted towards safer areas. For example, during the time of King Herod, the main port for the spice trade on this route on the Mediterranean coast was Caesarea, and during the Crusades, caravans from Petra, bypassed the conflict area, but this trade was never interrupted. Muslim dominance over the spice trade route forced Europeans to find alternate routes, ultimately leading to the Age of Discovery.

3. The Incense Road is a trade route that antiquity connected the south of the Arabian Peninsula with the countries of the Mediterranean and Mesopotamia from the ancient kingdoms on the territory of modern Yemen and Oman, as well as from the Horn of Africa and the Island of Socotra – mainly South Arabian incense, myrrh, and African spices. The widespread use of incense in the ancient East created a great demand for it and, therefore, caused extensive trade in these goods, which gave rise to the emergence of this trade route. The incense trade began in the 2nd millennium BC when Romans at the beginning of our era took control of the sea route to India and thereby jeopardized the coastal incense trade that was conducted through Aden, the capital of the Hadhramaut Shabwa state acquired the importance of an important trading center. Therefore, aromatic resins now had to be delivered to the port of Qana, 15 km west of today`s fisherman`s village of Bir Ali in Yemen, and from there to Shabwa. Incense from Somalia and Ethiopia also went to Cana. If the leaders of the camel caravans deviated from the established route, they faced the death penalty. In the desert, it was allowed to move only in organized caravans along strictly marked paths. Any deviation from these rules was considered the most serious crime and was

punishable by death. The wealth and importance of Shabwa lay in the city's position as an important gathering place for trade caravans to cross the great desert of the Rub al-Khali. Participants in the caravan had to pay one-tenth of the cost of the goods, which were given to the priests of the city temples in the name of the main goddess Siin. As per historical facts, there were 60 religious temples in Shabwa, and the city was the administrative and religious center of the ancient state of Hadhramaut. The population was obliged to bring the entire annual collection of aromatic resins to the temples of Shabva, and no one was allowed to export a single piece of resin outside the country. However, there were probably many attempts to violate this prohibition. Over time, the incense trade fell into decline and the shine of the South Arabian cities faded. Only rare caravans continued to walk along the old roads, laid long before the discovery of incense, transporting the salt necessary for life.

4. The Amber Route is an ancient trade route along which is antiquity Baltic amber was transported from the Baltic States to the Mediterranean. During the era of the Principate, the technique of processing amber, which was supplied to the city from the Baltic coast through the Roman province of Pannonia, reached a high level of development in Aquileia. From the port of Aquileia, amber goods sailed to Greece, Egypt, Syria, India, and other distant countries.

5. In Central Asia, two directions of trade routes were identified: Syrdarya and Amudarya trade in amber intensified from the middle of the 1st millennium BC., especially in the first centuries AD., up to the 5th century following along the Syrdarya, amber penetrates the Fergana Valley, actively covering its western and southwestern regions, and further east, to the borders of China. In the early Middle Ages, internal routes became more ramified. At the end of the twentieth century, as part of the protection of European cultural heritage, a program for creating tourist amber routes arose. They follow ancient routes from the Baltic Sea to the Mediterranean countries.

6. Tea Route – The Ancient Tea Route, or Chamagudao, originated during the Tang Dynasty 618-907 and reached its peak during the Song Dynasty 907 – 1270 when up to seven and a half tons of tea were transported to Lhasa annually. The routes of the ancient caravans of the tea route ran deep into the mountains in southwest China. These are some of the highest roads in the world – highways that connect Tibet mountain with the interior of the country, historical evidence of coexistence, and good neighborly relations between Han Chinese, Tibetans, and other peoples. Transportation was carried out both using horse-drawn transport and on foot.

7. Salt Road – The salt road is an ancient trade route along which salt was transported, which is also, reflected in the name of the road. The salt road provided Rome with a salt monopoly and became one of the sources of the city's prosperity. In Rome, the road began at the Porta Salaria of Aurelian's Wall and led through the interior of central Italy to the Camp of Truent on the Adriatic coast, a distance of 242 kilometers. Along the road, there are underground burials – catacombs, mostly Christian the cemeterial Jordanorum ad S. Alexandrorum, the catacombs of St.Panphil, Priscilla pagan and Christian burials, Trazon, St.Felice, Among others, Jason of Rome was buried here.

8. The Trans – Saharan trade route is very ancient. Along the two main roads crossing the desert from south to north, images, of chariots were found. From this, researchers concluded that trade routes ran through the Sahara in ancient times. The Garamantes who lived there were intermediaries in the trade of ivory, carbuncles, and slaves between the North, Carthage, Ancient Rome, and the South. The main caravan trade routes shifted several times. So, until the 11th century. The main caravan route passed through medieval Ghana, from the 12th century. He moved

east, connecting the Malian gold mines with the trading cities of North Africa. Malian gold, like many other goods, skins, ostrich feathers, etc, found their way to the Middle East and from there often to Europe. Since the 15th century, the main caravan route began to pass through Hausaland. The fall of medieval Mali at the end of the 15th century, the depletion of gold mines in the Bamboo region, and the formation of the large state formation of Songhai led to a shift in trade routes to the east from Western to Central Sudan. After the establishment of the sea routes between the coast of West Africa and Europe in the first half of the 19th century, trans-Saharan trade began to decline, however, it continued to exist until the end of the first quarter of the 20th century.

So, we can see that by history a global contradiction arose when the absolute overproduction of food in developed countries was accompanied by massive hunger and malnutrition in several third-world countries. This demonstrated that often chronic food instability is associated not so much with Malthus`s theory of diminishing returns or the underdevelopment of the agricultural sector but with the level of economic development and poverty of a significant part of the population of individual states, which makes food inaccessible at market prices. In this situation, the problem of food security of the population became the subject of close attention from the world community, and already in December 1974, the UN General Assembly approved the “International Commitments to Ensure Food Security in the World” developed by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations - FAO.

In 1996, the Rome Declaration of World Food Security was adopted at the World Food Summit. In this declaration, food security is defined as “a state of the economy in which the population of the country as a whole and each citizen individually is guaranteed access to food, drinking water and other food products in the quality, range, and volumes necessary and sufficient for physical and social development personality, ensuring health and expanded reproduction of the country's population” [2]. It is also noted that the source of food insecurity is poverty. Food security of the population in the terminology of the world literature is, first of all, determined by the macroeconomic situation, the efficiency of social production, and the income of the population. The state of food security of the population is assessed by a wide range of indications in

Fig. 1.

These include: - the share of food expenses in the total expenses of individual population groups, — the territorial availability of products, measured by comparing the level of retail prices

for the same goods in different regions of the country, - level of food “convenience” share in the consumption of modern products that reduce losses and save time in the household, - degree of “naturalness” and good quality of products, - the impact of product quality on health and life expectancy, including products obtained using genetic engineering and biotechnology methods, the mass commercial development of which began in 1995, etc, which is shown in Fig. 2.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In a generalized form, the assessment of the state of food security of the population [3], is determined by the physical availability of food – the availability of food throughout the country at each time and in the required range. Economic accessibility of food – the level of income, regardless of the social status and place of residence of a citizen, which allows the purchase of food at least at the minimum level of consumption. Food safety for consumers is the prevention of the production, sale, and consumption of low-quality food products that can harm public health. Food security occupies an increasingly important place in studies of socio-economic [4], political, environmental, demographic, managerial, biological, information, and technical, as well as in other scientific areas, which are relevant, complex, multifaceted, and multi-level. In this regard, it is difficult to offer one single definition of the scientific category of food security, which is presented in the three most significant official documents such as the “Rome Declaration on World Food Security and the World Food Summit Plan of Action” adopted in November 1996. The meaning of the above document remains relevant to this day. In October 2023, The Committee of World Food Security held its fifty-first session in Rome, “Reimagining Food Security and Nutrition”, which made recommendations to improve the collection and use of food security and nutrition data and appropriate analytical tools to improve decision-making and promote the progressive realization of rights for adequate nutrition in the context of ensuring national food security[5].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The economic essence of the system of financial support for food security is manifested in its components. Based on the above, the interaction of participants in the system of financial provision of food security consists of the state, agricultural producers, financial and credit

institutions, and the population that implements the organizational and economic mechanism as a whole [6]. Using the financial and economic levers, incentives, tools, and methods of regulating rules and regulations of the country's financial relations, each of the participants realizes their economic interests and contributions to the development of the system of financial support for food security. The combination of all elements of the financial law system and the obligations of the participants in financial legal relations is determined by relevant legislation that regulates economic relations between participants in the system of financial provision of food security. The elements of the food security financial system determine its main goal [7]:

- Formation of a financial basis for sustainable development of the agricultural sector of the economy;

- Increasing the competitiveness of domestic agricultural production.

- Socio – Natural Environment.

As you know, agricultural production is the basic sector for ensuring sustainable economic development. It is here that the quantitative and qualitative parameters that determine the further development and competitiveness of domestic food are formed, this is the first time agricultural producers had the required amount of financial and labor resources. High production efficiency was achieved in most economic entities. One of the achievements of the goal of the system of financial provision of food security create conditions for expanded reproduction, contributing to an increase in the volume of agricultural production and the share of Uzbekistan in the world market, which can ensure the food security of the state [8].

CONCLUSION

Subjects of the system of financial support for food security, depending on the nature of participation and role, can be the state, financial institutions, agricultural nature of participation and role, can be state, financial institutions, agricultural enterprises, and the population. The state, as a subject of the system of financial support for food security, by accumulating and redistributing financial resources, participates in creating conditions that provide the basis for expanded reproduction, participates in creating conditions that provide the basis for expanded reproduction, using tools such as creating a local fund that will be available for agricultural production and material and technical resources, leasing of agricultural machinery and breeding animals using budgetary funds, supporting crop insurance, financing, and investment activities in climate change era.

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